

DIGITAL LABOR IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract

Purpose – *The paper is dedicated to the analysis of opportunities stemming from digitalization, in terms of digital labor, as a tool for globalization. Throughout recent decades, globalization has become a strong force. This paper examines various aspects of digital labor.*

Methodology/approach – *The theoretical and methodological basis of the research is determined by a systematic approach which allowed defining the precise scope of this analysis. The methods combining logic, deduction and induction were used in the course of the research.*

Findings – *Globalization, technological innovation, and digitalization are among the most significant drivers of long-term growth. New digital systems offer tremendous benefits for the people. Objects, places, people, society are now being interconnected in a way that fundamentally changes the way we run everything, including labor.*

Research limitations/implications – *The development that we addressed is still in its inception and is expected to increase exponentially in the coming decades.*

Practical implications – *Development of digitalization creates favorable conditions for digital labor. Consequently, every country seeks opportunities for digitalization, on the basis of fast development of the digital technologies, to enter global markets.*

Originality/value – *Authors conceived and designed the study built on reviewed literature and on the statistical data.*

Key words: *globalization, digitalization, digital labor*

Introduction

From the beginning, digitalization has been associated to globalization, first being subordinated to globalization and then second, as an element increasing the speed of globalization. The relationship between globalization and digitalization is not inherently one-way but can evolve in tandem.

Globalized business processes, digitalization, enhanced international competition and the struggle for adaptation in order to integrate into the international environment set new challenges for the world's countries which need to be efficiently tackled in the shortest time possible. Understanding the role of the digital economy as an instrument of the globalization process is mandatory in order to establish priorities for the development of national economies that in turn will stimulate the development of our society. Digitalization both at the macro (i.e. country) and micro (i.e. organization) level is among the main priorities. Digitalization increases productivity, creates new jobs, and thus leads to overall economic growth.

In recent years the rapid growth of online platforms has been the focus of considerable studies. Online platforms allow individuals and organizations to exchange information and expertise more easily, rapidly and effortlessly than at any time in human history, thus promoting the growth of collective knowledge. Not being tied to the places where they live, workers are now able to do digital work which originates from anywhere. Digitalization brought jobs that might have not been available before in certain labor markets or locations.

Digitalization into the globalization framework

The corporate world is characterized by high complexity and dynamism, as well as by the globalization of competition and digitalization. Competition became considerably more intense in recent years because of the increased national border opening, growth of multinationals and digital networks. The economic success of the organizations depends on their ability to innovate. Innovation processes have greatly developed due to the decentralization of knowledge and talent centers and digital networking. The use of digital information and communication technology offers new possibilities, such as Internet-innovation networks, which are a basis for collaboration in science and research, thus enabling teamwork without limits in terms of time, geographical location and distance.

Digitalization can be described as using digital technologies to alter a business model and provide new prospects for revenues and value development, which means transitioning to a digital business. Digitalization is a technological drive that strengthens economic and cultural globalization. The digital economy produces new products, defines new needs and rises the speed and the amount of information every day.

The effect of digitalization on increased globalization can be seen in a variety of ways, including digital goods, improved flows of products and services, online networks, enhanced cross-border connectivity and globally dispersed teams. Nevertheless, labor and talent have been much slower to globalize relative to the movement of consumer goods and financial resources across countries.

In this scenario, there are some opportune questions: what effect does the economy's digitalization have on globalization processes? Does digitalization strengthen globalization? How does digitalization affect market features, organizational structure or job availability? What challenges does digitalization prepare for the workforce, for global economy and for us all?

Digital labor disregards the borders

People and their work have traditionally come as a single, completely integrated package, which makes location decisions complex. If someone or an organization seeks to access labor available abroad, one alternative is to attract and host the person, temporarily or permanently, near the location of the work that has to be performed. For different reasons this has proved to be politically controversial and almost every nation imposes limits on migration. A second alternative is to find out how the needed work can be shared at a distance, without requiring physical migration of the person. The horizon of time and location associated with the fulfillment of working tasks in another place or country has become a major force in business functions where tasks can be performed effectively at a geographical distance. The attention moves from "trade in goods" to "trade in tasks needed to be performed" (Grossman and Rossi-Hansberg, 2008).

Digitalization enables remote work across borders. Individuals create their own cross-border connections thanks to social media and to internet platforms. Individuals with imagination and motivation can launch themselves onto a global stage in ways that would have been impossible in the pre-digital era. Globally dispersed teams work together remotely across borders and in this way digitalization brings together talent from all over the world. Digital talent platforms have the capacity to better match the workers and the jobs, creating efficiency and transparency in labor markets (McKinsey Global Institute, 2017). Organizations can access a global pool of talent. Talented people from poor or developing countries are now able to compete with people from rich countries.

Besides all digital labor's advantages, a number of significant issues for workers also arise. One of the issues is the wide over-supply of labor force. This issue shows that sometimes there are ten times as many online job seekers on one platform as the workers who manage to get a job (Graham, Hjorth and Lehdonvirta, 2017). This excess in labor supply has the effect of reducing labor costs and limiting workers ability to negotiate for better conditions. Workers feel that they are competitors on global markets, recognizing that if they do not do a job or task at the level and conditions for which they were offered, someone else might do it. Another issue is that workers are considered self-employed rather than employees who deserve the rights of employees and could benefit from collective organization (Graham et al., 2017).

Digital labor across European Union (EU)

As we mentioned earlier, digital platforms provide to the people new ways to interact, collaborate, learn, develop new skills, find freelance work or a job to an employer to whom to showcase and prove the own talents. Digital labor has some mandatory basic requirements: internet access, digital technological equipment and proper digital skills. The EU's internal labor market has promoted cultural exchange and is currently the most common pillar of the EU (Barslund and Busse, 2014).

In 2019, 90 percent of households across Europe had internet access at home, through fix or mobile connections, up from 83 percent five years ago. In what regards the percent of EU citizens' use of mobile devices like mobile phones, laptops, tablets or other mobile devices in order to access the internet on the move via mobile or wireless connection, this was 75 percent in 2019 compared to 57 percent in 2015.

While already 90 percent of citizens used the internet in 2019, only 58 percent had at least basic or above basic overall digital skills. You cannot fully take advantage of digital technologies without the digital skills. Increased numbers of internet users do not automatically develop digital skills. Although, both basic and advanced digital skills have improved over the past years, the percentage of people with at least basic or above basic overall digital skills only slightly grew from 55 percent in 2015 to 58 percent in 2019. In 2019, the Netherlands and Finland were the EU's front-runners, while Bulgaria and Romania lagged behind, with a huge gap of almost 50 percent in between. However, a significant proportion of the EU population still lacks basic digital skills, while the majority of jobs require these skills. In school curricula across all EU countries, basic and advanced digital skills need to be improved.

In 2018, around 9.1 million people across the EU worked as Information and Communications Technology (ICT) specialists, 1.6 million more than four years earlier. Nevertheless, there is still a deficit of ICT specialists on the labor market: 64 percent of large companies and 56 percent of small and medium-sized enterprises that recruited ICT specialists in 2018 found it difficult to fill ICT specialist vacancies. The problem is even more common in Romania and Czech Republic, where these difficulties were identified by at least 80 percent of companies that recruited or tried to recruit ICT specialists. There is also an issue of gender balance, as only one in six ICT specialists is female.

The internet use rose continuously with 79 percent of Europeans surfing the internet every day or almost every day in 2019 compared to 67 percent in 2015. The figures refer to internet use in both private and work/business related circumstances. In 2019 the estimates range from 57 percent in Romania, 60 percent in Bulgaria to 90-92 percent in Finland, Sweden, Denmark and Netherlands. Furthermore, the percent of EU individuals that use the internet for sending/receiving e-mails was 75 percent in 2019 compared to 69 percent in 2015. In 2019 the figures range from 40-43 percent in Bulgaria and Romania to 90-94 percent in Finland, Netherlands and Demark. The use of video calls has risen the most, in just one year, since 2018 till 2019, the percent of internet users who were engaged in video calls grew from 49 to 60 percent. We have to point out the fact that in 2018 the percentage of EU's individuals working from home every day, almost every day or at least once a week but not every day was 5 percent and of those who used the internet for the job when working from home was 15 percent.

We have to mention that in 2019 the percent of individuals across EU using the internet for job search or sending a job application was 17 percent. The figures range from 32 percent in Finland, 30 percent in Sweden and 25 percent in Netherlands to seven, six and five in Bulgaria, Czech Republic and Romania, respectively.

Digital technologies influenced very quickly the economy and our society. The digital revolution offers a huge opportunity for society. It is one of the greatest forces for prosperity, employment and well-being nowadays and in the years to come. All countries need to be aware and to take advantage of these opportunities.

Tracking European Union (EU) digital performance and the access to digitization

The Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI)¹ monitors the overall digital performance of Europe and tracks EU countries' progress in digital competitiveness. Figure 1 presents EU Members States ranking on the 2020 DESI based on 2019 data.

Figure 1. Digital Economy and Society Index, 2020

Source: DESI 2020, European Commission

All EU countries enhanced their digital performance over the past years. Finland, Sweden, Denmark and the Netherlands achieved DESI 2020's highest scores and are among the world leaders in digitalization. It is necessary to underline the fact that EU large economies countries like Germany, Italy or France are not among the digital leaders in 2019. In what concerns the progress of European Member States as regards the overall level of digitization of the economy and society, over the last 5 years, the most notable improvement is noted in Ireland, followed by the Netherlands, Malta and Spain. Finland and Sweden, even though they are leading the list of the countries in matter of digital performance, they are marginally above average in terms of progress over the last five years. Little progress was also registered in the countries with a level of digitization below the EU average or in those that are placed at the end of the ranking, countries like Bulgaria, Greece and Romania. Nevertheless, all of these Member States have recently set up many initiatives, policies and measures in different areas tracked by the DESI. These initiatives require solid implementation and investments and the effects, hopefully, may be evident in the coming years. Nonetheless, there is still a long way to go for some countries, and in order to be able to compete on the global stage, the EU as a whole requires change.

¹ DESI overall index is calculated as the weighted average of the five main DESI dimensions with the weights selected by the user: Connectivity (fixed broadband take-up, fixed broadband coverage, mobile broadband and broadband prices), Human Capital (internet user skills and advanced skills), Use of Internet (citizens' use of internet services and online transactions), Integration of Digital Technology (business digitisation and e-commerce) and Digital Public Services (e-Government). The DESI 2020 reports are based on 2019 data. The United Kingdom is still included in the 2020 DESI, and EU averages are calculated for 28 Member States.

Conclusions

The evolution of digitalization made possible by robotics and artificial intelligence promises higher levels of efficiency, as well as increased protection and convenience. Digital technologies also change the world of work and generate whole new kinds of digital or virtual labor. Digitalization influences labor demand, skill requirements and organization of work. Both workers and businesses looking to expand in the digitalized world need new capabilities.

People with an internet connection and the basic or adequate digital skills can be employed in a wide variety of online activities. However, one of the key barriers to the digitization is the digital knowledge gap, which is caused by low rates of digital proficiency. Lack of digital skills decelerate further development of the society and economy. Adequate digital skills enabling people to access knowledge and resources are important for the entire population. Digital skills are mandatory for the successful and effective use of solutions for remote work and easier access to networks.

Digital labor associated with globalization is not limited by the national borders or by the national identities and it generates cultural mixing, transnational dialogue and collective knowledge. Under the unrestrained communication landscape provided by globalization and digitalization, the world feels like just one single nation. Even though digital communication gives access to, supports and intensifies multinational teamwork, the nation-centered framework is not weakening. This happens due to the fact that digital labor does not imply physical migration. Now, people have the opportunity to live in their native country, near their beloved ones, to enjoy their native customs and traditions and in the same time to work abroad through digital labor.

The emergence of the knowledge society ensures that economic growth is subordinated to the qualitative parameters of social and economic development. Future development would, after all, be dictated not only by the output of goods but also by the increased use of knowledge and talent. Digital labor paves the way to digital economy. Nowadays, to be able to handle competition, digital labor must be integrated into the global business environment.

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